

MACHINE LEARNING BASED PREDICTION OF CELL DEATH AFTER SILVER NANOPARTICLE TREATMENT

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Abstract:

Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are increasingly applied across biomedicine due to their antimicrobial and anticancer properties. However, concerns about their cytotoxicity to both cancerous and non-cancerous cells call for predictive tools that can accurately model their biological impact. In this study, we applied machine learning models to predict cell viability in response to AgNPs exposure using human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) and breast adenocarcinoma epithelial cells (MDA-MB-231) as biological models. Experimental data were collected at 24 h and 72 h post-treatment using a standard MTT assay. These data were used to train two machine learning models: Support Vector Regression (SVR) and Random Forest (RF). We then used each model to predict viability at 48 h and 96 h intervals not included in training and evaluated performance on unseen samples. SVR achieved RMSE of 1.61% at 48 h and 1.57% at 96 h outperforming RF (5.96% and 2.92%, respectively). Both models successfully generalized to unseen data and longer exposure durations. These results demonstrate the feasibility of using machine learning for nanotoxicology assessments enabling faster and more accurate predictions of cytotoxicity. These insights can significantly advance the safety evaluation of nanomaterials and support the development of safer nanoparticle based therapeutics.

Keywords: Silver Nanoparticles, Machine Learning, Cytotoxicity Prediction, Support Vector Regression (SVR), Nanotoxicology

1. Introduction

Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have gained attention in healthcare, medicine, and the food industry due to their unique physical and chemical features including high electrical conductivity and significant optical and thermal characteristics in addition to useful biological attributes [1, 2]. Utilizing these characteristics, AgNPs have been integrated as antibacterial agents in many different types of applications including household and industrial items, medical device coatings, cosmetics, orthopedic materials, diagnostics, drug-delivery systems, and consumer goods. Recently, they have been introduced to anticancer techniques, improving therapeutic efficacy by targeting malignant cells [3]. However, these advancements bring an unfair advantage. AgNPs can harm both malignant cells and healthy human tissues. Their nanoscale structure

imparts a "novel biological identity" causing physiological reactions that markedly differ from those of bulk silver and prompting considerable safety concerns [4]. A substantial corpus of toxicological research has emerged, addressing the safety of AgNPs using various *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* experiments [5]. However, different study designs and methodological choices resulted in inconsistent and at times insufficient results, limiting the ability to formulate generalizable conclusions on dose and time dependent toxicity [6]. A viable approach to address these constraints is to standardize data across research, enhancing both the human relevance and prediction accuracy of individual risk evaluations [7].

Machine learning provides a powerful solution to these challenges [8]. By modeling the intricate, non-linear interactions among nanoparticle (NPs) characteristics, exposure parameters, and biological effects, machine learning approaches can produce high throughput, precise predictions of cytotoxicity reducing the necessity for extensive manual testing [9-11]. This study applied two robust algorithms, Support Vector Regression (SVR) [11] and Random Forest (RF) [10] to predict cell viability parameters after AgNPs treatment. Our experimental framework involves viability assessments of human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) and MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells that received AgNPs treatment. Standard MTT tests performed at 24 hours and 72 hours post-treatment provide the training data for both SVR and RF models. We then applied each model to predict viability at intermediate (48 h) and extended (96 h) time points, assessing performance on unseen samples. Our results demonstrate that SVR outperforms RF and generalizes effectively across exposure durations. By integrating machine learning into the nano-toxicology pipeline, we establish a benchmark for the rapid, reliable prediction of AgNPs cytotoxicity. Such predictive tools are essential for guiding the design of safer, commercially viable nano-enabled products and for streamlining regulatory evaluation in the expanding nano-biomaterials market.

2. Methodology

2.1. Cell culture and Cell Viability Analysis

This part has already been explored in our previous publication [12]. The investigations were conducted using human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) and breast adenocarcinoma epithelial cells (MDA-MB-231) as model cell lines for atherosclerosis and cancer, respectively. From European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures, we got our cell lines. The following steps were taken to conduct the cell viability experiments according to already published scientific approach [13]. In a 96-well plate, 10,000 cells were planted in 100 μ l of medium each well. For 24 hours, the plate was incubated in CO₂ at 37 °C to ensure cell adhesion. Six repetitions of 100 μ l fresh medium and varying quantities of VMT-AgNPs (10, 20, 40, 60 μ g/ml) dissolved in cell medium were added to wells. The control group was only cell media. For another 24 and 72 h, the plate was incubated at 37 °C in CO₂. After incubation, media was evacuated from each well and 100 μ l of complete medium and 25 μ l of 5 mg/ml MTT solution were added. The plate was incubated for 4 h in CO₂ at 37 °C. Afterward, MTT-containing medium was withdrawn from each well and 150 μ l of DMSO was added. The plate was dark-incubated for 20 min. Finally, 492 nm absorbance was measured to examine findings.

2.2. Machine Learning Approaches in Cellular Response Prediction

A. Data Preprocessing

The dataset was carefully preprocessed where numerical features such as Time, Dose, *in-vitro* Data, and Coefficient were normalized using standard scaling. The categorical variable representing "Cancerous" or "Non-Cancerous" was transformed via one-hot encoding to ensure proper input format for the models. The entire dataset was partitioned into training and testing subsets using an 80/20 split. Importantly, we ensured that the same test set was consistently used for evaluating both the Support Vector Regressor (SVR) and the Random Forest (RF)

models. This approach guarantees that comparisons between the models' predictive performances are fair. After performing training on known data and testing on the unseeded data (i.e., the initial split from the original dataset), a new set of unseen samples was later applied to further test the models' generalizability.

B. Model Development

In this study, two advanced machine learning techniques were implemented. The first method, the Support Vector Regressor (SVR), leverages statistical learning theory to capture the subtle, non-linear relationships in the data. By minimizing an error function that carefully balances model complexity with prediction tolerance, the SVR is tailored to provide robust predictive performance. In parallel, the Random Forest (RF) model employs an ensemble learning strategy by aggregating predictions from multiple decision trees, each built on a bootstrapped subset of the data. This approach inherently mitigates overfitting and efficiently models the complex non-linear trends present in biological systems.

C. Hyperparameter Optimization

Both the SVR and Random Forest models underwent meticulous hyperparameter tuning combined with systematic cross-validation to minimize the mean squared error. For the SVR model, critical parameters such as the regularization coefficient, epsilon parameter, kernel-specific parameters, and polynomial degrees were finely tuned to optimize its performance. Similarly, for the Random Forest model, the grid search process focused on determining the optimal number of trees, maximum tree depth, minimum number of samples required to split an internal node, minimum number of samples needed at a leaf node, and the number of features considered during each split, ensuring that its configuration was robust and well-optimized.

D. Model Evaluation

Both models were evaluated on a consistent test set representing 20% of the data, ensuring a fair performance comparison. The primary metric used for evaluation was the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), which is calculated as

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}$$

where y_i represents the actual values, \hat{y}_i represents the predicted values, and N is the number of observations. This measure quantifies the average magnitude of prediction errors and provides a single metric of model accuracy—lower RMSE values indicate predictions that are closer to the observed outcomes. Following training and testing on the unseeded data from the original split, new unseen samples were further utilized to validate the models. This additional validation step provided an extra layer of performance verification, confirming that the predictive frameworks can effectively generalize to truly novel data.

3. Results and Discussion

A comprehensive evaluation of the Support Vector Regression and Random Forest models was conducted to predict cell viability following AgNPs treatment under varying doses and time. Both models were trained on laboratory collected data at 24 and 72 hours. As shown in Table 1, both models achieved very low RMSE, demonstrating strong predictive accuracy for dose and time dependent cell viability. These findings underscore the potential of machine learning methods in revealing subtle dose and time dependent patterns of cellular response, highlighting how data-driven approaches can augment traditional toxicological analyses.

Table 1: Observed Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) on Unseen Data

Model	Time	RMSE
Support Vector Regressor	48h	1.61%
	96h	1.57%
Random Forest	48h	5.96%
	96h	2.92%

3.1. Performance on Support Vector Regression (SVR)

The Support Vector Regression (SVR) model was applied to eight new unseen samples for predicting outcomes at 48 hours, encompassing four non-cancerous and four cancerous samples at concentrations of 10, 20, 40, and 60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Table 1 presents these unseen input values along with their corresponding predicted results. The SVR model exhibited strong predictive performance, indicated by a low Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), demonstrating that the predicted values consistently fell within the range of observed experimental values, effectively capturing the underlying trends with acceptable deviations. The predictions obtained from these samples were subsequently integrated into the existing dataset, thereby expanding it to include results at 24-hour, 48-hour, and 72-hour intervals. Leveraging this augmented dataset, the SVR model was then employed to predict the outcomes at the 96-hour time point, facilitating an extended validation of the model performance and its ability to generalize to longer exposure durations. Figure 1 and Figure 2 illustrate the trends of the predicted values alongside the original experimental values, highlighting the SVR model's accuracy and its ability to closely follow the observed data patterns across different concentrations and time points.

Table 2: Sample Unseen Data for SVR Prediction at 48h and 96h

Dose (%)	Data	Coefficient	Cell Type	48h Predicted (%)	96h Predicted (%)
10	1.105	1.725	Non-cancerous	65.36	55.7261
20	0.554	1.725	Non-cancerous	28.9848	30.1812
40	0.511	1.725	Non-cancerous	26.0539	19.7849
60	0.214	1.725	Non-cancerous	7.9767	11.5264
10	0.512	0.523	Cancerous	83.2028	61.6847
20	0.435	0.523	Cancerous	70.3787	40.1253
40	0.151	0.523	Cancerous	24.6899	22.0061
60	0.1	0.523	Cancerous	16.8908	19.694

Figure 1: SVR Predicted Values at 48h on Non-Cancerous and Cancerous Cells

Figure 2: SVR Predicted Values at 96h on Non-Cancerous and Cancerous Cells

3.2. Performance on Random Forest (RF)

The Random Forest (RF) model was applied following the same methodology as SVR approach. It was applied to predict outcomes at 48-hour using the eight new unseen samples (four non-cancerous and four cancerous at 10, 20, 40, and 60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). Table 3 shows these unseen samples alongside their corresponding RF predicted results. The predictions were then integrated into the existing dataset (covering 24, 48, and 72 h samples) and used to predict outcomes at 96 hours. Using a combined evaluation set of 16 additional test samples and 83 laboratory verified results, the RF model achieved low RMSE value demonstrating its ability

to generalize to longer exposure durations. Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the predicted values alongside the observed experimental data across different concentrations and time highlighting the RF model performance and its capacity to capture the underlying trends effectively.

Table 3: Sample Unseen Data for RF Prediction at 48h and 96h

Dose (%)	Data	Coefficient	Cell Type	48h Predicted (%)	96h Predicted (%)
10	1.03	1.725	Non-Cancerous	60.5014	59.5444
20	0.538	1.725	Non-Cancerous	32.2631	31.4874
40	0.319	1.725	Non-Cancerous	27.9506	18.381
60	0.092	1.725	Non-Cancerous	11.1262	7.0288
10	0.743	0.523	Cancerous	88.8499	84.7376
20	0.444	0.523	Cancerous	73.5395	70.082
40	0.124	0.523	Cancerous	23.9678	20.4175
60	0.0707	0.523	Cancerous	15.8533	13.9442

Figure 3: RF Predicted Values at 48h on Non-Cancerous and Cancerous Cell

Figure 4: RF Predicted Values at 48h on Non-Cancerous and Cancerous Cell

4. Discussion

The present study demonstrates the considerable promise of machine learning (ML) techniques for predicting cellular responses to silver nanoparticle (AgNPs) exposure [14]. By leveraging Support Vector Regression (SVR) and Random Forest (RF) models, we achieved exceptionally low RMSE values—no greater than 6%. This level of agreement falls well within the typical 5–10% variability observed in in-vitro assays due to differences in experimental conditions, underscoring that, when properly trained, ML models can replicate traditional cytotoxicity assessments with high fidelity [15]. A key advantage of ML-based prediction is the reduction in time and resources required [10]. Conventional cytotoxicity testing often entails extensive cell culture, reagent preparation, and multiple time-point measurements each of which adds cost and potential for variability. In contrast, a well-trained ML model can generate accurate viability forecasts in seconds, enabling rapid screening of NPs formulations and experimental protocols without the need for exhaustive bench work [16]. This streamlined approach accelerates the design–build–test cycle, facilitating quicker decision-making in both research and regulatory contexts [4]. Central to the success of ML modeling is the quality and breadth of the training data. In our framework, the inclusion of 24 h and 72 h MTT measurements across multiple doses and cell types provided the diversity necessary for robust

model learning. It is well-established that model performance improves as both the size and representativeness of the dataset increase. Indeed, the variance in predicted versus observed values tended to shrink as more training examples were included. Consequently, expanding the dataset, both in terms of sample count and the range of AgNPs characteristics, will further enhance predictive accuracy and extend the applicability domain of the models. Equally important is thoughtful feature selection. In this work, time point, AgNPs concentration, cell type, and experimentally derived coefficients constituted our input features. Models built on these carefully chosen predictors captured the essential drivers of cytotoxic response. Irrelevant or noisy features, by contrast, can introduce overfitting and degrade generalization. As such, future efforts will explore automated feature-engineering pipelines, such as recursive feature elimination or embedded methods, to identify the most informative descriptors from a larger pool of nanoparticle physicochemical properties and biological readouts. Looking ahead, we plan to scale the dataset to hundreds of experimental samples, incorporating a broader spectrum of NPs sizes, shapes, surface chemistries, and cell models. This enriched dataset will support the training of more expressive neural network-based architectures, such as deep feed-forward networks or graph neural networks that have demonstrated superior performance in other nanomaterials applications. These advanced models hold the potential to uncover subtle, high-dimensional interactions between nanoparticle features and cellular responses, further reducing prediction error and broadening the scope of *in silico* toxicology.

In summary, our findings validate machine learning as a fast, reliable alternative to traditional cytotoxicity assays when applied with rigorous data collection and feature-selection strategies. By extending our approach to larger, more diverse datasets and harnessing next-generation neural network algorithms, we anticipate developing predictive tools that not only match but surpass the throughput and accuracy of bench experiments—paving the way for safer, more efficient development of nano-enabled therapeutics and products.

5. Conclusions

This study successfully demonstrates the integration of machine learning models, specifically Support Vector Regression (SVR) and Random Forest (RF), for predicting AgNPs-induced cytotoxicity across cancerous and non-cancerous human cell lines. Through rigorous training, testing, and hyperparameter optimization, both models were able to accurately forecast cell viability at multiple time points and dosages. Among them, the SVR model consistently showed superior performance with significantly lower RMSE values, especially on unseen data at 48h and 96h, highlighting its robustness in generalizing to novel biological scenarios. The findings underscore the potential of data-driven approaches in complementing traditional toxicological assessments, offering a more rapid, cost-effective, and scalable means of evaluating nanoparticle safety. Moreover, by extending the dataset to include additional prediction intervals and validating across diverse cell types, this framework sets a precedent for future nanotoxicity modeling. It offers a strategic advantage in the design of safer nanoparticle formulations, reducing reliance on extensive *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* testing. In the rapidly expanding field of nanomedicine, where precision and personalization are critical, such predictive models represent a significant leap forward. Continued refinement and expansion of these models may ultimately facilitate regulatory compliance and enhance public confidence in nanotechnology-based therapies and consumer products.

Author's contribution

SURQ designed and conducted the *in-vitro* experiments, and WURQ performed the AI models for predictive analysis. SURQ and WURQ wrote the original draft. NF supervised the experiments and acquired the funding.

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